

A SUPERCONGRUENCE INVOLVING CUBES OF CATALAN NUMBERS

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Abstract

We mainly show a supercongruence for a truncated series with cubes of Catalan numbers which extends a result due to Zhi-Wei Sun.

1. Introduction

This short paper grew out as a complement to the author's recent paper [9], where various supercongruences for truncated series of ${}_3F_2(1)$ were provided.

Let us consider the sum

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \left(\frac{C_k}{4^k} \right)^d$$

where d is a positive integer and $C_k = \frac{1}{k+1} \binom{2k}{k}$ is the k -th Catalan number.

For $d = 1$ and $d = 2$, it is easy to find a closed formula:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{C_k}{4^k} = 2 - \frac{\binom{2n+1}{n}}{4^n} \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{C_k^2}{16^k} = -4 + (5 + 4n) \frac{\binom{2n+1}{n}^2}{16^n}.$$

Thus, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we are able to evaluate the series

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_k}{4^k} = 2 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_k^2}{16^k} = -4 + \frac{16}{\pi}.$$

Moreover, for any prime $p > 2$, the above explicit formulas allow getting the congruences

$$\sum_{k=0}^{(p-1)/2} \frac{C_k}{4^k} \equiv_{p^2} 2 - 2(-1)^{(p-1)/2} p, \quad \sum_{k=0}^{(p-1)/2} \frac{C_k^2}{16^k} \equiv_{p^3} -4 + 12p^2$$

where we use the notation $a \equiv_m b$ to mean $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$.

On the other hand, when $d = 3$, it seems that there is no closed formula for the partial sum. However, by Dixon's theorem [1, p.13], we find

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_k^3}{64^k} = 8 \left(1 - {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2} \\ 1, 1 \end{matrix}; 1 \right] \right) = 8 - \frac{384\pi}{\Gamma^4(\frac{1}{4})}.$$

What about the related congruence? We are going to show that for any prime $p > 2$, a surprisingly *similar* formula modulo p^3 holds:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{(p-1)/2} \frac{C_k^3}{64^k} \equiv_{p^3} \begin{cases} 8 - \frac{24p^2}{\Gamma_p^4(\frac{1}{4})} & \text{if } p \equiv_4 1, \\ 8 - \frac{384}{\Gamma_p^4(\frac{1}{4})} & \text{if } p \equiv_4 3, \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

where Γ_p is Morita's p -adic Gamma function which is defined as the continuous extension to the set of all p -adic integers $\mathbb{Z}_p$ of the sequence

$$n \rightarrow (-1)^n \prod_{\substack{0 \leq k < n \\ (k,p)=1}} k$$

(see [6, Chapter 7] for a detailed introduction to Γ_p).

The above congruence (1) modulo p has been established by Zhi-Wei Sun in [7, Theorem 1.2]. Modulo p^2 , the case $p \equiv_4 1$ is implied by [8, Theorem 1.3] (see also [4, Theorem 1.1]).

After some preliminary work done in the next section, the proof of (1) will be given in the third section.

2. A Bunch of Identities

The following one-parameter formula is the identity 6.34 in Gould's collection [3] (for $j = 0$ see [2]):

$$\sum_{k=0}^n A(n, k, j) = \frac{1 + (-1)^{n-j}}{2} \binom{n+j}{(n+j)/2} \binom{n-j}{(n-j)/2} \tag{2}$$

where

$$A(n, k, j) = \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k+j} (-4)^{n-k}.$$

We have that

$$\frac{A(n, k, 1)}{A(n, k, 0)} = 1 - \frac{1}{k+1},$$

and, by (2), we get

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k}}{(-4)^k (k+1)} = \frac{\binom{2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}^2}{16^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}} \cdot \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n \equiv_2 0, \\ \frac{n}{n+1} & \text{if } n \equiv_2 1. \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

In like manner, by using the partial fraction expansion,

$$\frac{A(n+1, k+1, 1) - (n^2 - n)A(n, k, 2)}{A(n, k, 0)} = 4 + n - n^2 + \frac{4n^2 + 4n - 2}{k+1} - \frac{2n(n+1)}{(k+1)^2},$$

and

$$\frac{A(n+1, k+1, 0)}{A(n, k, 0)} = 4 + \frac{8n+2}{k+1} + \frac{4n^2-2}{(k+1)^2} - \frac{2n(n+1)}{(k+1)^3},$$

yield respectively

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k}}{(-4)^k (k+1)^2} = \frac{\binom{2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}^2}{16^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}} \cdot \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } n \equiv_2 0, \\ \frac{2n^2 + 2n - 1}{(n+1)^2} & \text{if } n \equiv_2 1, \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k}}{(-4)^k (k+1)^3} = -\frac{2}{n(n+1)} + \frac{\binom{2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}^2}{16^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}} \cdot \begin{cases} \frac{(2n+1)^2}{n(n+1)} & \text{if } n \equiv_2 0, \\ \frac{4n^4 + 8n^3 + 3n^2 - n + 1}{n(n+1)^3} & \text{if } n \equiv_2 1. \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

We would like to point out that, along the same lines, we are able to provide a closed formula for

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{Q(k) \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k}}{(-4)^k (k+1)^3}$$

where Q is any polynomial in $\mathbb{Z}[x]$. For example

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{k^3 \binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k}}{(-4)^k} = \frac{\binom{2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}^2}{16^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}} \cdot \begin{cases} \frac{n^2(n+1)^2(2n+1)^2}{15} & \text{if } n \equiv_2 0, \\ -\frac{n^2(4n^4 + 8n^3 + 3n^2 - n + 1)}{15} & \text{if } n \equiv_2 1. \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

Moreover, by using the same approach outlined in [9, Lemma 4.2], we get two key identities which play a major role in the proof of our main result. For any positive

even number n ,

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k} H_{k+1}^{(2)}}{(-4)^k (k+1)^3} = \frac{\binom{n}{n/2}^2}{4^n} \left(16 + \frac{(2n+1)^2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k^2}}{n(n+1)} \right) - \frac{4^n}{\binom{n}{n/2}^2} \cdot \frac{4n^4 + 8n^3 + 3n^2 - n + 1}{n^3(n+1)^3}, \tag{7}$$

whereas for any positive odd number n ,

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k} H_{k+1}^{(2)}}{(-4)^k (k+1)^3} = \frac{\binom{n-1}{(n-1)/2}^2}{4^{n-1}} \left(\frac{(4n^4 + 8n^3 + 3n^2 - n + 1) \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k^2}}{n(n+1)^3} + \frac{16n^8 + 64n^7 + 92n^6 + 52n^5 + 5n^4 - 2n^3 + 2n^2 + n + 1}{n^3(n+1)^5} \right) - \frac{4^{n-1}}{\binom{n-1}{(n-1)/2}^2} \cdot \frac{(2n+1)^2}{n^3(n+1)} \tag{8}$$

where $H_k^{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^k 1/j^r$ is the k -th harmonic number of order $r \geq 1$.

3. Proof of Supercongruence (1)

First of all, we need a stronger version of Lemma 3 of [9]: for any prime $p > 3$,

$$\frac{\binom{2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}^2}{16^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}} \equiv_{p^2} \begin{cases} -\Gamma_p^4 \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{p^2 E_{p-3}}{2} \right) & \text{if } p \equiv_4 1, \\ \frac{16 + 32p + p^2(48 - 8E_{p-3})}{\Gamma_p^4 \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)} & \text{if } p \equiv_4 3, \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

where $n = (p - 1)/2$ and E_k is the k -th Euler number. Indeed, for $p \equiv_4 3$,

$$\frac{\binom{2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}^2}{16^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}} = \frac{\Gamma_p^2 \left(\frac{p+3}{4} \right)}{\left(\frac{p-1}{4} \right)^2 \Gamma_p^2 \left(\frac{p+1}{4} \right)} \equiv_{p^3} \frac{\Gamma_p^2 \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) \left(1 - \frac{(-1)^n}{16} p^2 H_{\lfloor p/4 \rfloor}^{(2)} \right)^2}{\left(\frac{p-1}{4} \right)^2 \Gamma_p^2 \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)} \equiv_{p^3} \frac{16 + 32p + p^2(48 - 8E_{p-3})}{\Gamma_p^4 \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)}$$

because, by [5, (20)], $H_{\lfloor p/4 \rfloor}^{(2)} \equiv_p (-1)^n 4E_{p-3}$.

The proof for the case $p \equiv_4 1$ is similar:

$$\frac{\binom{2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}^2}{16^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}} = -\frac{\Gamma_p^2 \left(\frac{p+1}{4} \right)}{\Gamma_p^2 \left(\frac{p+3}{4} \right)} \equiv_{p^3} -\frac{\Gamma_p^2 \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{(-1)^n}{16} p^2 H_{\lfloor p/4 \rfloor}^{(2)} \right)^2}{\Gamma_p^2 \left(\frac{3}{4} \right)} \equiv_{p^3} -\Gamma_p^4 \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) \left(1 + \frac{p^2 E_{p-3}}{2} \right).$$

Furthermore, for $0 \leq k \leq n$,

$$\binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} (-1)^k = \binom{2k}{k} \frac{\prod_{j=1}^k ((2j-1)^2 - p^2)}{4^k (2k)!} \equiv_{p^3} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}^2}{16^k} \left(1 - p^2 \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{(2j-1)^2} \right).$$

Hence, by (5) and (9), congruence (1) is implied by

$$\sum_{k=0}^{(p-1)/2} \frac{C_k^3}{64^k} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{(2j-1)^2} \equiv_p \begin{cases} -8 - \frac{24}{\Gamma_p^4(\frac{1}{4})} - 4\Gamma_p^4\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) & \text{if } p \equiv_4 1, \\ -8 + \frac{192(5 - E_{p-3})}{\Gamma_p^4(\frac{1}{4})} & \text{if } p \equiv_4 3, \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

which is interesting in its own right. In order to show (10), notice that

$$\frac{C_k}{4^k} \equiv_p \frac{(-1)^k}{k+1} \binom{n}{k} = \frac{(-1)^k}{n+1} \binom{n+1}{k+1}$$

and, since $H_n^{(2)} \equiv_p 0$ (see [5, (19)]), it follows that

$$\sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{(2j-1)^2} \equiv_p \frac{1}{4} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{(n+1-j)^2} = \frac{H_n^{(2)} - H_{n-k}^{(2)}}{4} \equiv_p -\frac{H_{n-k}^{(2)}}{4}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{(p-1)/2} \frac{C_k^3}{64^k} \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{(2j-1)^2} &\equiv_p \frac{1}{4(n+1)^3} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{k+1} \binom{n+1}{k+1}^3 H_{n+1-(k+1)}^{(2)} \\ &= \frac{(-1)^n}{4} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k}^3 \frac{H_{k+1}^{(2)}}{(k+1)^3} - \frac{H_{n+1}^{(2)}}{4(n+1)^3} \\ &\equiv_p \frac{(-1)^n}{4} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\binom{n}{k} \binom{n+k}{k} \binom{2k}{k} H_{k+1}^{(2)}}{(-4)^k (k+1)^3} - 2H_{n+1}^{(2)} \end{aligned}$$

and we find (10) from (7), (8), (9),

$$H_{n+1}^{(2)} \equiv_p H_n^{(2)} + 4 \equiv_p 0 + 4 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k^2} = -H_n^{(2)} + \frac{H_{\lfloor p/4 \rfloor}^{(2)}}{2} \equiv_p 0 + (-1)^n 2E_{p-3}.$$

□

As a final remark, we notice that, following the same procedure, from identity (6), we find that for any prime $p > 5$,

$$\sum_{k=0}^{(p-1)/2} \frac{k^3 \binom{2k}{k}^3}{64^k} \equiv_{p^3} \begin{cases} -\frac{p^2}{40\Gamma_p^4(\frac{1}{4})} & \text{if } p \equiv_4 1, \\ -\frac{2}{5\Gamma_p^4(\frac{1}{4})} & \text{if } p \equiv_4 3. \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

This congruence modulo p appeared in [7] whereas, the case $p \equiv_4 1$ modulo p^2 is implied by Theorem 1.3 of [8].

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